

THE FORMATION OF MULTILINGUAL COMPETENCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7972555>

ANNOTATION

Each new period in the history of society entails a number of issues, and development is impossible, if there are no solutions to them. This article deals with the analysis of peculiarities of modern multilingual education, which is vital for the preparation of specialists in many spheres. Today a special attention is given to mastering a foreign language, since in the 21st century a person is increasingly perceived not only as a citizen of a particular country, but as a citizen of the world. Multilingual competence is a successful learning outcome within the multilingual educational process. It is concluded that teaching a foreign language should be carefully balanced with teaching a native language.

Key words: bilingual, competence, first language, personality, intercultural, communication, conscious, unconscious.

Nowadays, the living conditions of people have changed significantly, especially particular place occupies human mobility, both in personal and professional life in life. Exercise the performance of a wide variety of professional responsibilities is increasingly associated with study and knowledge of one or more foreign languages. It is natural that one of the main directions in the development of modern education is multilingualism. In the XXI century a special role is assigned to learning new foreign languages, it is inextricably linked with the formation of a multicultural, multilingual personality with communicative and intellectual needs, abilities and competencies that will allow them to successfully operate in the conditions of intercultural communication and professional-linguistic activity in the role of a subject of foreign language knowledge, foreign language communication and foreign language creativity.

In fact, multilingualism is not a new term or a new phenomenon. Scholars from different parts of the world learned several languages and were responsible for the translation of official records and religious books into different languages.

Multilingual is a person who speaks several foreign languages. Byrd Clark (2009) defines multilingualism as "a special linguistic personality with distinctive competence - a set of personal characteristics and a number of key competencies that are formed in the process of mastering the second, third foreign languages". Block, D. (2008) notes "multilingual is also characterized by multiculturalism - a quality based on the synthesis of tolerance, empathy and reassessment of one's own culture"

Psychologists argue that, by its social nature, the phenomenon of multilingualism should be perceived not as a loss, but as an enrichment of one's own cultural identity.

Multilingual education

L.M. Malykh (2016) investigates models of teaching a foreign language in pre-university educational institutions. According to the him, multilingual education is aimed at successfully mastering a new foreign language and at the same time deepening and improving the native language and native culture.

It should be noted that the conceptual apparatus used while working with multilingual processes in education has not yet been fully formed. In this study, I made an attempt to highlight such issues related to the formation of the multilingual competence of the individual as a model of multilingual education, the features of modern higher education aimed at the formation of the multilingual personality of the student and the components of the multilingual personality, which should be formed in the course of studying and working with several foreign languages.

In most of the schools in Uzbekistan, the most common model of multilingual education is teaching a second foreign language (first is Russian), which is usually English. As a second language German, French and Spanish are also can be taught. However, in this case, there is a significant difference between the first and second foreign languages and the fact that mastering the second foreign language seems to be overlaid on mastering and working with the first. The leading principles of teaching in the implementation of this model are communicative-cognitive and contrastive principles.

In the context of in-depth study of a foreign language in secondary schools, a model of teaching on a bilingual basis can be implemented. This model is based on the mastery of subject knowledge based on the interrelated use of two languages as a means for the implementation of educational activities. In the course of training, the language should be perceived "as a tool for introducing the world of special knowledge" (Gauker,1987). The author notes that a special role in this case is played by the combination of subject and language components at all levels of the educational process.

Ethno-lingua didactics is defined as "teaching foreign languages in conditions of multilingualism and natural bilingualism of the local population" (Borgoyakov et al., 2021). In the implementation of this model, the natural bilingualism of students and their background knowledge about the people and people living in close vicinity, whose languages they speak, is involved. At the same time, in the process of learning languages, the role of multicultural education is especially taken into account. Respect and understanding of the cultures of other people are becoming one of the main tasks of ethno-lingua didactics.

If the foreign languages taught at school are genetically related, we can talk about the implementation of the next model of multilingual education - the simultaneous teaching of several related languages. The goal in this case is to teach students in a relatively short period of time to read and comprehend oral speech in one of the related languages. Learning to comprehend written and spoken language is built through the formation of receptive skills. This model is developed in maximum detail on the basis of the languages of the Romance group.

It should be noted that not all models are listed above. It is rather difficult to draw a clear distinction between them, and their complementarity is often noted in the process of teaching a foreign language. Common to all is "taking into account the interference of previously learned languages on a new language of instruction, finding ways to use a new language to enhance the cognitive development of students" (Shelly,1998).

Multilingual Personality and Multilingual Competence

The educational process within the framework of classroom bi-multilingualism "allows students to familiarize themselves with the richness of world culture and prepare them for quick adaptation to the demands and requirements of a dynamically changing world. Multilingualism and multiculturalism are related, and through multilingualism students can be drawn into the topic of multiculturalism, starting from what they already know, with their experiences as language learners. Multiculturalism and multilingualism are both key aspects of the world they live in and they should know about. They also need to understand this world, and one step is to sympathize with different culture" (Drobot, 2021).

In this multicultural world the status of a teacher changes significantly. Instead of only providing information necessary for work and teaching the student certain knowledge, skills and abilities, the teacher becomes a kind of consultant and advisor who must teach the student to independently work with a foreign language and foreign language culture, explain Aurora & Duncan (1986).

Ponterotto (2010) emphasizes that one of the main issues in the framework of multilingual education at the moment is the question of the formation of a *multilingual personality*, who "ensures the development and social stability of the world society as a whole".

Today, the literature does not have a single well-established set of competencies required for foreign language training of students. Researchers distinguish linguistic/ linguistic, sociolinguistic, sociocultural, social, discourse/ speech, compensatory, activity, educational, strategic competence.

In his research, Eun Young Kang, (2013) gives an explanation of the term "multilingual competence", which should be formed within the framework of multilingual education. This competence is defined as "the ability and willingness to solve urgent problems of communication by means of foreign languages and to achieve the goal of interaction and mutual understanding with representatives of different cultures and languages, to develop and consistently apply an individual style of mastering languages and cultures, to use the most appropriate educational and communication strategies".

Within this competence, the author distinguishes three competencies: strategic, multilingual and sociocultural. It should be noted that other previously listed competencies are not excluded, but are integral parts of the designated components.

The highlighted three competencies have points of contact; therefore, the development of one always goes along with the development of the other. But at different stages of training, attention can be paid to different competencies.

Multilingual competence is based on strategic competence, most fully and clearly formulated by Cenoz, J., & Genesee, F., (1998). "the ability to develop various short-term and long-term plans for the use of verbal and non-verbal means of overcoming difficulties in communication and learning / mastering the language, which are designed to take effect whenever there is a need to search for solutions to real or anticipated problems in the course of communication or learning activities". A multilingual person with this competence can use universal communication and learning strategies. Universal strategies "are used by multilinguals in solving both educational and communication problems".

In turn, the universal strategies are divided into metacognitive, social-affective and compensatory. Communication strategies are "communication strategies as potentially

conscious plans to overcome what appears to be a difficulty for a multilingual to achieve a communicative goal (Evdokimova, N,2009).

According to Cenoz and Gorter (2013), strategies are “a number of intellectual techniques used to understand, memorize and use the knowledge of the language system and to form speech skills and abilities”. An orientation towards individual characteristics is important for the authors when applying strategies to students. To master this strategic competence, students must not only master the listed strategies, they must get to know themselves and develop their own style of comprehending languages.

The next competence as part of the multilingual competence is language competence, “which presupposes possession of knowledge about the system of languages and the corresponding skills of operating linguistic means of communication associated with different levels of language” Within this competence, lexical, grammatical, semantic and phonetic competences are distinguished for different levels of the language.

In this case, the authors emphasize that the main feature of this competence is not so much linguistic knowledge and skills, but the systemic perception of languages.

The third competence included in the multilingual competence is sociocultural competence, presented as “the willingness and desire of students to interact with others, the ability to conduct a dialogue of cultures and independently act in various social situations (Safonova, 2009). Especially in this case, personal developmental potential should be taken into account, since with the development of a new language, a person expands the framework of his attitude and worldview.

In the process of forming this competence, there are three components: self-determination, awareness of culture as a theoretical construct and entering into a dialogue with other cultures. Safonova (2009), considers the peculiarity of mastering this competence “mastering the planetary consciousness, which is characterized by the ability of a person to consider himself not only as a representative of national culture (pass) but also as a citizen of the world, who perceives himself as a subject of the dialogue of cultures and realizes his role and responsibility in global human processes”.

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